

Insect Juvenile Hormone Analogues. Part—XX : Synthesis and Juvenile Hormone Activity of Geranyl and Citronellyl Aromatic Ethers and Their Derivatives

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Geranyl and citronellyl bromides are condensed with different substituted phenols (2-isopropylphenol, 4-isopropylphenol, 5-isopropyl-2-methylphenol and 6-isopropyl-3-methylphenol) in the presence of a base to give their respective ethers. These ethers have been modified at the terminal double bond to give various derivatives. All these compounds have been tested for their juvenile hormone (JH) activity against *Dysdercus koenigii fabricus*.

IN continuation of our earlier work on the synthesis and JH activity of some undecenyl aromatic ethers^{1,2} and study of the effect of different substituents on the aromatic ring and conversion of the terminal double bond into the corresponding epoxy, dichloromethylene, dibromomethylene and tertiary carbinol derivatives, the present work was undertaken to prepare a variety of compounds and to study their structure-activity relationship.

2-Isopropylphenol, 4-isopropylphenol, 5-isopropyl-2-methylphenol and 6-isopropyl-3-methylphenol were alkylated with geranyl bromide in the presence of sodium hydride and THF³ to give the ethers I-IV, and with citronellyl bromide in refluxing acetone³ containing anhyd. K₂CO₃ to afford the ethers V-VIII. This change in reaction condition was necessitated because of the formation of elimination products with the use of NaH as a base. The ethers I-IV and V-VIII were epoxidized⁴ with one equivalent of *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid in dry methylene chloride to yield the monoepoxy derivatives IX-XII and XIII-XVI, respectively.

I in chloroform with triethylbenzylammonium chloride⁵ in the presence of aq. NaOH produced 1-(2'-isopropyl phenoxy)-10,11-dichloromethylene XVII in good yield. Under similar conditions, II-IV and V-VIII furnished the dichloromethylene derivatives XVIII-XX and XXI-XXIV, respectively. Treatment of I-VIII with bromoform and triethylbenzylammonium chloride in aq. NaOH gave the dibromomethylene derivatives XXV-XXXII. I-VIII on mercuration-demercuration³ yielded alcohols XXXIII-XL.

The ethers, epoxides dichloromethylenes, dibromomethylenes and tertiary carbinols thus prepared are listed in Table 1 along with their characterisation data. Their elemental analyses and spectral data (ir, pmr) were consistent with their structures. Spectral data in a few representative cases have been given. The boiling points of some of the deriva-

tives could not be recorded due to paucity of the samples.

All the compounds (tlc-pure) were tested for their JH activity against *Dysdercus koenigii fabricus* according to the procedure reported in literature^{3,6} using farnesyl methyl ether as standard (activity index = 4.00)⁷. The testing results (Table 2) showed the ethers I-VIII to be fairly active, whereas the corresponding oxiranes were found to be far more active having the maximum activity index of 4.00. On the other hand, the dichloromethylene and dibromomethylene derivatives were found to be moderately active having the activity index in the range 2.10-3.50. However, the tertiary carbinol derivatives XXXIII-XL were found to be less potent than the parent ethers, excepting for XXXVII, XXXVIII having the activity 3.10 and 3.33, respectively. The presence of C-2 double bond in geraniol showed no significant change in activity in comparison to citronellol.

Experimental

1-(2'-Isopropyl phenoxy)-3,7-dimethyl-2(E),6-octadiene (I): To a stirred suspension of sodium hydride (2.68 g, 50%; 55 mmole) in THF (40 ml) was added dropwise a solution of 2-isopropylphenol (6.8 g; 50 mmole) in THF (20 ml) at 0°. The mixture was stirred for additional 2 hr at room temp. followed by dropwise addition of geranyl bromide (10.85 g; 50 mmole) in THF (20 ml). This was stirred overnight and the contents were then refluxed for 8 hr. The reaction mixture was decomposed with cold water and the organic layer was separated. The organic layer was washed successively with 10% NaOH solution, brine and dried. After removal of the solvent, the residue was chromatographed over neutral alumina eluting with *n*-hexane to afford I, yield 70%, (9.52 g), b.p. 150-55°/3-4 mm. (Found: C, 83.65; H, 10.52. C₁₉H₂₈O requires C, 83.77; H,

TABLE 1—CHARACTERIZATION DATA OF THE COMPOUNDS PREPARED

Compd. no.	b.p. °C/mm	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)		
				C	H	X*
II	160-62/2-3	72	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O	83.59 (83.77)	10.52 (10.36)	—
III	162-65/3-4	67	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O	83.75 (83.86)	10.72 (10.56)	—
IV	180-85/5-6	72	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O	83.92 (83.86)	10.65 (10.56)	—
VI	162-65/2-3	62	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O	83.29 (83.15)	10.83 (11.02)	—
VII	142-45/1-2	60	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O	83.05 (83.27)	11.35 (11.18)	—
VIII	140-42/1-2	64	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O	83.10 (83.27)	11.30 (11.18)	—
X	—	48	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₂	78.95 (79.12)	9.65 (9.79)	—
XI	—	47	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₂	79.35 (79.42)	9.89 (10.00)	—
XII	—	45	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₂	79.25 (79.42)	9.85 (10.00)	—
XIII	—	47	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₂	78.71 (78.57)	10.59 (10.41)	—
XIV	—	48	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₂	78.42 (78.57)	10.65 (10.41)	—
XV	—	48	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₂	79.05 (78.89)	10.45 (10.59)	—
XVI	—	50	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O	78.65 (78.89)	10.42 (10.59)	—
XVIII	—	47	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ OCl ₄	57.34 (57.53)	6.51 (6.39)	32.19 (32.42)
XIX	—	48	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ OCl ₄	58.25 (58.40)	6.72 (6.63)	31.55 (31.41)
XX	—	52	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ OCl ₄	58.19 (58.40)	6.89 (6.63)	31.25 (31.41)
XXI	—	52	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ OCl ₂	67.42 (67.22)	8.53 (8.40)	19.63 (19.88)
XXII	—	54	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ OCl ₂	67.51 (67.22)	8.19 (8.40)	19.75 (19.88)
XXIII	—	45	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ OCl ₂	67.64 (67.92)	8.75 (8.62)	19.32 (19.14)
XXIV	—	52	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ OCl ₂	67.72 (67.92)	8.37 (8.62)	19.51 (19.14)
XXV	—	49	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ OBr ₄	41.07 (40.90)	4.32 (4.54)	52.17 (51.94)
XXVI	—	52	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ OBr ₄	40.62 (40.90)	4.62 (4.54)	52.07 (51.94)
XXVII	—	52	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ OBr ₄	42.07 (41.90)	4.82 (4.76)	50.85 (50.79)
XXVIII	—	46	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ OBr ₄	42.12 (41.90)	4.89 (4.76)	50.62 (50.79)
XXIX	—	49	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ OBr ₂	54.05 (53.81)	6.52 (6.72)	36.12 (35.87)
XXX	—	48	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ OBr ₂	53.57 (53.81)	6.92 (6.72)	36.09 (35.87)
XXXI	—	43	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ OBr ₂	54.62 (54.78)	7.15 (6.95)	34.85 (34.78)
XXXII	—	50	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ OBr ₂	54.92 (54.78)	7.13 (6.95)	34.52 (34.78)
XXXIV	165-67/1-2	45	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₂	78.65 (78.57)	11.32 (10.41)	—
XXXV	170-75/3-4	50	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₂	79.06 (78.89)	10.75 (10.59)	—
XXXVI	155-57/2-3	47	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₂	78.76 (78.89)	10.80 (10.59)	—
XXXVII	155-60/2-3	52	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₂	77.83 (78.03)	11.25 (11.03)	—
XXXVIII	172-75/2-3	45	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₂	77.85 (78.03)	11.22 (11.03)	—
XXXIX	150-55/1-2	50	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₂	78.52 (78.38)	11.27 (11.18)	—
XL	160-62/2-3	54	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₂	78.55 (78.38)	11.32 (11.18)	—

*X represents Cl or Br.

TABLE 2—JUVENILE ACTIVITY OF COMPOUNDS (I-XL)

[No. of insects used=10; dose=1% in acetone (6 μ l)]

Compd.	Dead	Activity response					Activity indices
		0	1	2	3	4	
I	0	1	3	1	2	3	2.90
II	0	0	1	3	2	4	2.90
III	1	0	4	0	2	3	2.44
IV	0	1	5	2	2	0	1.50
V	0	0	1	2	0	7	3.30
VI	0	0	2	0	0	8	3.40
VII	0	1	3	0	5	1	2.20
VIII	1	0	4	1	2	2	2.20
IX	0	0	3	1	2	4	2.70
X	0	0	1	0	1	8	3.60
XI	1	0	2	0	1	6	3.22
XII	0	1	2	1	2	4	2.60
XIII	1	2	2	0	1	4	2.33
XIV	0	0	0	0	0	10	4.00
XV	2	0	2	0	1	5	3.12
XVI	1	1	3	0	1	4	2.44
XVII	1	0	2	0	5	2	2.77
XVIII	2	0	0	0	6	2	3.25
XIX	0	0	2	0	3	5	3.10
XX	2	0	0	0	4	4	3.50
XXI	0	0	2	2	3	3	2.70
XXII	0	0	0	2	5	3	3.10
XXIII	0	1	2	1	3	3	2.50
XXIV	0	0	4	2	1	3	2.30
XXV	0	0	2	1	5	2	2.70
XXVI	0	0	0	2	6	2	3.00
XXVII	0	0	3	1	2	4	2.70
XXVIII	0	0	3	0	3	4	2.80
XXIX	0	1	3	0	3	3	2.40
XXX	0	1	3	0	2	4	2.50
XXXI	1	1	2	2	2	2	2.22
XXXII	0	1	4	0	3	2	2.10
XXXIII	0	2	3	2	0	3	1.90
XXXIV	1	0	2	3	1	3	2.80
XXXV	1	3	3	2	1	0	1.11
XXXVI	0	2	4	1	1	2	1.70
XXXVII	0	0	1	2	2	5	3.10
XXXVIII	1	0	2	0	0	7	3.33
XXXIX	0	4	3	1	2	0	1.10
XL	1	3	3	1	2	0	1.22

10.36%). IR : 2920, 1600, 1460, 1400, 1360, 1305, 1250, 1210, 1165, 1100, 1055, 1020, 895, 825, 750 cm^{-1} . PMR (CCl_4) : δ 1.21 {6H, *d*, $J=7.5$ Hz, -Ar-CH(CH_3)₂}, 1.63, 1.68, 1.73 (9H, 3 *s*, allylic methyls), 2.1 (4H, allylic methylenes), 3.33 {1H, *m*, -Ar-CH(CH_3)₂}, 4.53 (2H, *d*, $J=6$ Hz, -CH₂-O-Ar), 5.1 (1H, *t*-like, C₆-olefinic proton), 5.5 (1H, *t*, $J=6$ Hz, C₂-olefinic proton), 6.9 (4H, *m*, -Ar-H).

Similarly, compounds II-IV were prepared by treating geranyl bromide with 4-isopropylphenol, 5-isopropyl-2-methylphenol and 6-isopropyl-3-methylphenol to yield the respective ethers.

1-(2'-Isopropyl phenoxy)-3,7-dimethyl-6-octene (V) : A mixture of 2-isopropylphenol (3.4 g; 25 mmole), anhyd. potassium carbonate (20 g; 145 mmole), dry acetone (150 ml) and citronellol bromide (5.5 g; 25 mmole) was refluxed for 10 hr. The contents were cooled, filtered and the filtrate concentrated. The residue was taken up in ether, washed with 10% aq. NaOH and water. After drying and solvent evaporation the residue was chromatographed over neutral alumina, using *n*-hexane as the eluent to afford V, yield 60%, (4.1 g), b.p. 140-45°/2-3 mm. (Found : C, 82.97; H, 11.23. C₂₀H₃₀O requires C, 83.15; H, 11.02%). IR : 2920, 1620, 1480, 1400, 1305, 1255, 1210, 1165, 1100, 1050, 895, 795, 750 cm^{-1} . PMR (CCl_4) : δ 0.97 (3H, *d*, $J=6$ Hz, C₈-methyl), 1.25 {6H, *d*, $J=6$ Hz, -Ar-CH(CH_3)₂}, 1.55-2.2 (13H, allylic methyls, saturated methylenes, allylic methylene and C₈-proton), 3.3 {1H, *m*, -Ar-CH(CH_3)₂}, 3.97 (2H, *t*, $J=6$ Hz, -CH₂-O-Ar), 5.1 (1H, *br.t.*, olefinic proton), 6.95 (4H, *m*, -Ar-H).

Compounds VI-VIII were prepared in the similar way by the reaction of citronellol bromide with corresponding phenols in the presence of K₂CO₃ in acetone.

1-(2'-Isopropyl phenoxy)-3,7-dimethyl-6,7-epoxy-2(E)-octene (IX) : To a well stirred ice cold solution of I (0.68 g; 2.7 mmole) in anhyd. methylene chloride (40 ml) was added dropwise *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid (0.475 g; 2.7 mmole) in anhyd. methylene chloride (20 ml). After the addition, the mixture was stirred for 45 min at 0° and 30 min at room temp. and then poured into cold water. The organic layer was separated, washed successively with sodium bicarbonate solution, water and dried (CaCl₂). After removal of the solvent, the residue was chromatographed over florisil to give IX, yield 48%, (0.346 g). (Found : C, 78.97; H, 9.92. C₁₈H₂₈O₂ requires C, 79.12; H, 9.79%). IR : 2920, 1600, 1470, 1400, 1310, 1250, 1210, 1165, 1135, 1100, 1055, 1015, 880, 755, 685 cm⁻¹. PMR (CCl₄) : δ 1.2 {12H,

$\begin{array}{c} \text{O} \\ \diagup \quad \diagdown \\ -\text{Ar}-\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2 \text{ and } -\text{CH}-\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2 \end{array}$

1.55 (2H, saturated methylene), 1.75 (3H, *s*, allylic methyl), 2.2 (2H, *t*, *J*=7.5 Hz, allylic methylene), 2.53 (1H, *t*, *J*=6 Hz, oxirane methine proton), 3.33 {1H, *m*, -Ar-CH(CH₃)₂}, 4.53 (2H, *d*, *J*=7.5 Hz, -CH₂-O-Ar), 5.54 (1H, *t*, *J*=7.5 Hz, olefinic proton), 6.9 (4H, *m*, -Ar-H).

Similarly, compounds X-XII and XIII-XVI were obtained from II-IV and V-VIII respectively by treating with *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid.

1-(2'-Isopropyl phenoxy)-3,7-dimethyl-2(3),6(7)-bis-dichloromethylene-octane (XVII) : A solution of I (0.68 g; 2.7 mmole) in chloroform (15 ml) and triethylbenzylammonium chloride (0.143 g) was stirred until the salt dissolved. To this, aq. sodium hydroxide (50%, 2.5 ml) was added and stirring continued for 3 days. The reaction mixture was decomposed with water and aqueous layer extracted with chloroform. The combined organic layer was dried (CaCl₂), the solvent removed and the residue chromatographed over florisil to obtain XVII, yield 52%, (0.7 g). (Found : C, 57.65; H, 6.21; Cl, 32.57. C₂₁H₂₈OCl₂ requires C, 57.33; H, 6.39; Cl, 32.42%). IR : 2880, 2805, 1565, 1460, 1430, 1350, 1265, 1215, 1100, 1070, 1025, 800, 740 cm⁻¹. PMR (CCl₄) : δ 1.16-1.85 {21H, saturated methylenes, -Ar-CH(CH₃)₂,

$\begin{array}{c} \text{CCl}_2 \qquad \qquad \qquad \text{CCl}_2 \\ \diagup \quad \diagdown \qquad \qquad \diagup \quad \diagdown \\ (\text{CH}_3)_2\text{C}-\text{CH}- \text{ and } -(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{C}-\text{CH}- \end{array}$

3.33 {1H, *m*, -Ar-CH(CH₃)₂}, 3.9, 4.45 (2H, -CH₂-O-Ar), 7.0 (4H, *m*, -Ar-H).

In the same way, compounds XVIII-XX and XXI-XXIV were prepared from II-IV and V-VIII respectively.

The same procedure was adopted for the preparation of compounds XXV-XXXVIII and XXIX-XXXII from I-IV and V-VIII, respectively using bromoform instead of chloroform.

1-(2'-Isopropyl phenoxy)-3,7-dimethyl-2(E)-octene-7-ol (XXXII) : I, (2.72 g, 10 mmole) was added with efficient stirring at room temperature to a yellow solution of mercuric(II) acetate (3.5 g; 11 mmole) in water (8 ml) and THF (50 ml). The colour of the solution disappeared in a few min after the addition of I. The reaction mixture was stirred for another 2 hr, cooled and alkaline sodium borohydride (0.2 g in 10 ml 3 *N* NaOH) added. The organic layer was separated, aq. layer was saturated with NaCl, extracted with ether and dried. After removal of the solvent the residue was chromatographed over neutral alumina to afford XXXII, yield 51%, (1.48 g), b.p. 160-62°/1-2 mm. (Found : C, 78.45; H, 10.55, C₁₈H₂₈O₂ requires C, 78.57; H, 10.41%). IR : 3350, 2900, 1610, 1500, 1460, 1420, 1300, 1250, 1200, 1165, 1140, 1110, 1055, 820, 750 cm⁻¹. PMR (CCl₄) : δ 1.2 {12H, -CH₂-(OH)C(CH₃)₂ and -Ar-CH(CH₃)₂}, 1.37-1.66 (5H, saturated methylenes and -OH proton exchangeable with D₂O), 1.7 (3H, *s*, allylic methyl), 2.07 (2H, *t*-like, allylic methylene), 3.3 {1H, *m*, -Ar-CH(CH₃)₂}, 4.53 (2H, *d*, *J*=6 Hz, -CH₂-O-Ar), 5.5 (1H, *t*, *J*=6 Hz, olefinic proton), 6.9 (4H, *m*, -Ar-H).

Similarly, compounds XXXIV-XXXVI and XXXVII-XL were prepared from II-IV and V-VIII, respectively.

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